

Implementing disclosure controls in DataSHIELD demonstrated by the dsSurvival package

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The Cox proportional hazards model is one of the most popular survival analysis models used to determine the importance of predictors in survival. Achieving sufficient power in survival analysis usually requires large amounts of data from several sites or institutions. However, due to the ethical and practical considerations related to data transmission, and institutional policies, individual-level data cannot be shared in many situations. As an alternative, the DataSHIELD framework (based on the statistical programming language R) can be used. Here, the individual-level data remain at each site and only anonymous, aggregated data are shared. By carefully implementing disclosure controls in each DataSHIELD function, privacy of the individual-level data is ensured. It is complex to build and verify the disclosure controls and therefore a limited number of DataSHIELD functions are available.

To address this problem, we have developed the package *dsSurvival* for building Cox proportional hazards models using individual-patient data that are distributed across several sites, without moving those data to a central site. We will present the package and discuss potential disclosure risks and how we addressed those. Specifically, we propose a framework, for ensuring privacy control, where only the relevant non-disclosive statistical summaries will be shared. Additionally, we add a privacy control which prevents the fitting of Cox models where the number of parameters are less than a pre-set fraction of the number of entries in the survival data. Our tool can be of great use in domains where there is a need for building privacy-preserving survival models.